

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D6.10 – Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 1

Co-funded by the European Union

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

This project has received funding from the Horizon Innovation Actions under the grant agreement n° 101096405.

SCAN QR CODE

About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

Contact Email: contact@up2030-he.eu

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	101096405	Acronym	UP2030	
Full Title	Urban Planning and Design ready for 2030			
Start Date	01/01/2023	Duration	36 months	
Project Website	https://up2030-he.eu/			
Deliverable	D6.10 - Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives			
Work Package	WP6 UP-TAKING - Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Sustainability of UP2030			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	30/06/2024	Actual	21/06/2024
Nature	R - Report	Dissemination Level	PU-Public	
Lead Beneficiary	ICLEI			
Author(s)	Katherine Peinhardt (ICLEI), Elena Petsani (ICLEI)			
Reviewer(s)	Vasiliki Papageorgiou (DreVen), Catalina Diaz (Fraunhofer), Alisa Krumm (USTUTT), Constanza Vera (USTUTT)			
Abstract	The D6.10 Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives outlines the ways in which UP2030 works with related and sister projects to enhance impact, as well as with broader initiatives like the EU Mission: Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities.			

Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
0.1	17/05/2024	Draft	Design of table of contents	ICLEI
0.2	21/05/2024	Draft Review	Review of Table of contents and Executive Summary	Fraunhofer
0.3	30/05/2024	Draft	First version of the Deliverable	ICLEI
0.4	06/06/2024	Draft Review	Review of first draft	DreVen
0.5	14/06/2024	Draft	Second version of the Deliverable	ICLEI
0.6	18/06/2024	Draft Review	Coordination Review	Fraunhofer & USTUTT
1.0	21/06/2024	Final	Final version ready for submission	ICLEI

Disclaimer

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the EUROPEAN UNION or the EUROPEAN CLIMATE, INFRASTRUCTURE AND ENVIRONMENT EXECUTIVE AGENCY (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

The content, format, citations, and sources presented in this report are the sole responsibility of the author. While efforts have been made to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the content presented, there may be gaps in the information provided, or the information may become outdated over time. Readers are encouraged to independently verify any information presented in this report to ensure its accuracy and relevance to their specific needs or circumstances.

Copyright message

© UP2030 Consortium, 2023

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Contents

Executive summary.....	6
Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables.....	6
Acronyms.....	7
1 Introduction.....	8
1.1 Purpose and Scope.....	8
1.2 Document Structure.....	8
2 Objectives of clustering activities with other Mission initiatives	9
2.1 Roadmap for collaboration.....	9
2.1.1 Core Cluster	11
2.1.2 Exchange Cluster.....	12
3 Clustering activities.....	13
3.1 Clustering activities with Core Cluster.....	13
3.1.1 Interactions undertaken	13
3.1.2 Planned activities.....	13
3.2 Clustering activities with Exchange Cluster	16
3.2.1 Interactions undertaken	16
3.2.2 Planned activities	16
3.3 Documentation of activities	16
4 Conclusions.....	17

Figures

Figure 1: Core (in green) and Exchange Clusters (in purple) for Collaboration	10
Figure 2: Objectives of the Core Cluster (in green) and Exchange Cluster (in purple).....	12

Tables

Table 1: Prior Meetings of related projects and initiatives to date of writing.....	10
Table 2: Core Cluster Overview	11

Table 3: Exchange Cluster Overview 12

Table 4: Core Cluster activities 15

Table 5: Exchange Cluster Activities 16

Executive summary

This document outlines activities planned and undertaken by UP2030 to connect and cluster with the Cities Mission, NetZeroCities (NZC), and related Mission projects (CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value). It outlines two main streams of clustering activities based on a “core cluster” and an “exchange cluster,” and describes a roadmap for specific points of engagement with these groups.

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the work packages’ structure. Therefore, the content of this document has been developed in alignment with ICLEI, Fraunhofer, and relevant projects CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value. The following table lists the deliverables that were input for this present document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the presented content.

Input from	Contributes to
<i>Roadmap: Collaboration with the Mission and related projects</i> (internal operational document)	D6.11 Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 2 (M36) D6.12 – Sharing UP2030 best practices and policy briefs with the Mission’s platform (M36)
Mil. 2: Launch of UP2030 visual identification and virtual presence, and initial D&C plan (M3)	

The target audiences for this deliverable are UP2030 project partners, as well as relevant project consortia and pilots/followers e.g., sister projects CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value. Further audiences include NZC, the Cities Mission Secretariat, and stakeholders involved in the EU Mission: Adaptation to Climate Change. This will guide the project for the remainder of its lifetime in terms of its clustering and collaboration with relevant initiatives, with an update in the form of deliverable D6.11 (M36). The content of the report will be shared within the UP2030 consortium, as well as with CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value partners. It is also a public deliverable that will be available on the UP2030 project website.

Acronyms

Acronym	Full name
CoM	Covenant of Mayors
D	Deliverable
M	Month
Mil	Milestone
NZC	NetZeroCities
PO	Project Officer
T	Task
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

Deliverable 6.10 (D6.10) Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives is a precursor to an updated version, D6.11 Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 2, which will be submitted by the end of the project's lifetime (M36) and will summarise activities undertaken as a follow-up to D6.10.

1.2 Document Structure

The document is organised as follows:

- ❖ Section 1 - Introduction: Description of the purpose and scope of the document and its structure
- ❖ Section 2 - Objectives of clustering activities with other Mission initiatives clustering activities with other Mission initiatives
- ❖ Section 3 – Clustering activities
- ❖ Section 4 - Summary and Next Steps

2 Objectives of clustering activities with other Mission initiatives

UP2030 aims to collaborate with other related projects and Mission initiatives in order to collaboratively enhance impact, avoid duplication of efforts, improve reach to target audiences, and jointly work towards achieving the broader goals of the EU Mission: Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities. These goals are part of *Task 6.4 (T6.4) Collaboration with the Mission and related projects (M1-M36)* as defined in the UP2030 Grant Agreement, which includes provisions to “build synergies between UP2030 and other Mission initiatives and projects to enhance the dissemination range and wider end-user community, as well as accelerate the cities’ progress.” Among these synergies are the identification of cross-cutting themes between related projects and initiatives, joint dissemination activities, and knowledge exchange.

To that end, UP2030 partners (primarily ICLEI and Fraunhofer) have further refined these objectives into two main areas on which to focus clustering activities: **1. Enhance dissemination impact and define cross-cutting themes;** and **2. Raise awareness/impact of the projects to the Cities Mission.** These are outlined in a dynamic working document shared with and periodically reviewed by related projects (CLIMABOROUGH, Re-Value), titled *Roadmap: Collaboration with the Mission and related projects*. The structure of the roadmap is outlined in the following subchapter 2.1 and is the basis for this deliverable. The working document is considered a living one and will be considered internal to the consortium until that time that it is annexed to the further edition of this deliverable, *D6.11 Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 2 (M36)*. The roadmap outlines shared plans for clustering and collaboration activities with the aforementioned related projects. It goes further to include interactions with NetZeroCities (NZN), the Cities Mission Secretariat, and the EU Mission: Adaptation to Climate Change, alongside initiatives like the Covenant of Mayors (CoM), Smart Cities Marketplace, and Scalable Cities Initiative.

2.1 Roadmap for collaboration

As part of T6.4, UP2030 has developed an internal, operationally focused *Roadmap: Collaboration with the Mission and related projects*, upon which this deliverable is based. The dynamic roadmap document delineates a collaboration concept with two levels of engagement: A “Core Cluster” with CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value projects; and a broader “Exchange Cluster” with NZC, the Cities Mission Secretariat, and the Mission Adaptation, alongside initiatives like the CoM, Smart Cities Marketplace, and Scalable Cities. These two clusters have been conceptualised with different key aims and different key activities, elaborated in Sections 2.1.1 and 2.1.2 below (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Core (in green) and Exchange Clusters (in purple) for Collaboration

Broader Cluster Coordination Meetings that spanned both the Exchange and Core Cluster partners have already taken place (see table below and Section 3.1 for further details). Moving forward, the Core Cluster will continue to meet, focusing on working groups defined in Section 3. The Exchange Cluster will be involved and informed about key outcomes and opportunities identified within the Core Cluster, as appropriate.

Table 1: Prior Meetings of related projects and initiatives to date of writing

Meetings	Attendees
<p>Cluster Coordination</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> February 2023, March 2023, June 2023, January 2024 June 2024 (EURESFO) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH, Re-Value partners, CINEA Mission Secretariat (only for February 2023) NZC, (only for February 2023)
<p>Cluster Work Group</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> June 2024 (Core Cluster) Further meetings forthcoming 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Core Cluster <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication and dissemination working group Knowledge generation and exchange working group Exchange Cluster on ad hoc basis, depending on Core Cluster meeting topics

In terms of longevity and legacy of this work, UP2030 has kick-started this collaboration with the above-mentioned roadmap, which will be carried forward through partners involved in cluster projects, (e.g. ICLEI is involved in Re-Value and could carry activities forward throughout its lifetime, which extends beyond that of UP2030). The structures and communication routes established in this document can be sustained in this way, as well as through things like groups created on platforms like the NZC Portal, etc.

2.1.1 Core Cluster

Table 2: Core Cluster Overview

Involvement	Objectives
UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH, Re-Value, cities involved in these projects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhance dissemination and maximise impact for the project outcomes for the cities, and Identify cross-cutting themes across the three Mission Projects

The identified **Core Cluster**, which is taking the leading role in the implementation of the clustering activities, includes the consortium members of the three Mission Projects UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH, and Re-Value, as well as involved cities. For this cluster, the objective is twofold: **enhance dissemination and maximise impact for the project outcomes for the cities and identify cross-cutting themes across the three Mission Projects**. This takes the form of:

- Building synergies among the Core Cluster and with the other groups of stakeholders (Exchange Cluster)
- Collaborating on dissemination
- Identifying cross-cutting themes between cluster members/projects
- Fostering city exchange on Best Practices
- Exploring opportunities for outputs related to cross-cutting themes (e.g., policy recommendations)

The first steps of involving this Core Cluster took the form of composing the aforementioned roadmap, a document that has also been reviewed jointly with CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value to define an action plan. During this discussion of the roadmap, two working groups were identified (see Section 3.1.1 for more details): **Knowledge generation and exchange working group; Communication and dissemination working group**.

To maximise the impact of the projects’ outcome on the cities, it is important to build synergies with all the different levels of stakeholders from the Cities Mission. As the primary target group of this is cities, it is important that this working group closely collaborates with beneficiaries of the Mission Projects and extends its activities as much as possible, reaching the cities that are part of the NZC programme as well as the other Exchange Cluster parties (see Figure 2 below). Specific measures to reach these audiences are outlined in Section 0 below.

Structure

- 1 Enhance dissemination/impact, find cross cutting themes
- 2 Raise Awareness/Impact of the project to the Mission

Figure 2: Objectives of the Core Cluster (in green) and Exchange Cluster (in purple)

2.1.2 Exchange Cluster

Table 3: Exchange Cluster Overview

Involvement	Objectives
UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH, Re-Value alongside EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change and associated projects, Relevant Initiatives, Cities Mission Secretariat	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify opportunities and channels/events for joint dissemination alongside Cities Mission, NZC, and related Mission projects • Survey key project milestones suited to joint dissemination and create dissemination packages to be shared with Exchange Cluster members

A secondary “Exchange” Cluster takes the scope of clustering activities for UP2030 wider to include NZC, the Cities Mission Secretariat, the Mission Adaptation, CoM, Smart Cities Marketplace, Scalable Cities, and more. For these initiatives, the objectives centre on identifying opportunities for joint dissemination and surveying key project milestones that are well-suited for dissemination. These opportunities are identified as part of the Core Cluster activities – and will be pursued through the working groups therein (See Section 3.1.1).

3 Clustering activities

3.1 Clustering activities with Core Cluster

3.1.1 Interactions undertaken

The Core Cluster activities will build on and expand existing exchange meetings, some of which involved the Project Officer (PO) directly. These initial PO-facilitated clustering meetings took place on February 2023, March 2023, June 2023, January 2024, and June 2024. Moving forward, these activities will be structured into regular Core Cluster Meetings among the projects identified in Section 2 above, ensuring a more systematic and strategic approach to collaboration. This new regularity (aiming for meetings every 3 months, as elaborated below) will enhance the coordination and planning of joint activities, fostering deeper and more consistent engagement among the participating cities and projects. Through this structured approach, the Core Cluster aims to strengthen partnerships, streamline collaborative efforts, and drive forward their shared objectives for Climate Neutrality and Urban Resilience.

The discussions in these meetings centred on establishing two working groups: one for **knowledge generation and exchange** and another for **communication and dissemination**. The former group will facilitate (both through meetings and online software designed for collaboration and file-sharing) the exchange of plans and experiences among various projects, focusing on overcoming barriers, ensuring lasting impacts, and identifying game changers like innovative procurement and capacity building. They will pursue themes identified among UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value: publications and open science; knowledge exchange. This group aims to evolve organically and work towards outputs like the production of a joint scientific publication.

The latter communication and dissemination group will use the above-mentioned software tools designed for remote collaboration and file sharing as a starting point to organise common and local events. They will explore joint publication opportunities, practical cooperation methods such as shared hashtags and calendars, and ways to benefit the broader community of cities involved in the projects, with the Re-Value communication team leading this effort. This group will also pursue a specific theme identified by UP2030, CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value: events, communication of cluster outcomes.

The latest update of the roadmap was done jointly by the Cluster projects in May 2024 to prepare the main objectives and the action points to be discussed in the upcoming Clustering Meeting in June 2024 in Valencia.

Joint presence at events has already begun, including so far:

- EURESFO 2023 in Cascais, Portugal – Common Session Integrated Climate-Neutral and Resilient Cities: Exploring Innovative Urban Planning and Design Practices focusing on the district approach
- EURESFO 2024 in Valencia, Spain – Common presence at the Marketplace as the Urban Planning and Design Cluster

3.1.2 Planned activities.

UP2030 will have **regular operational Core Cluster Meetings** with Re-Value and CLIMABOROUGH to plan collaboration activities – with **meetings every 3 months** as an initial goal. This Core Cluster could be governed using the structure of a rotating co-chair position for an involved city from one or more of the projects (with, as needed, ICLEI as co-chair supporting a rotating city role).

Among the three Core Cluster projects, partners will coordinate **simultaneous presence at two or more events** (e.g., EURESFO annual meeting, NZC Annual Conference, World Urban Forum, etc.). This will include

the pitching of sessions including all Cluster Projects, and/or application for joint Marketplace spaces, among other ideas. Cluster Project partners will also be **invited to the UP2030 Final Conference in 2025**, in order to share finalised results and takeaways which should take place on the second half of that year. Already, a dedicated session EURESFO 2023 took place in Cascais, Portugal– paving the way for further collaboration on a shared Marketplace stand at EURESFO 2024 in Valencia, Spain, the planning for which is currently underway. Additionally, an Urban Planning Forum is being coordinated for 2025 with the specific timing (Summer or Autumn) yet to be determined.

The Core Cluster projects (UP2030, Re-Value, and CLIMABOROUGH) will select events for simultaneous presence based on several specific criteria. Primarily, events must align with the projects' core themes of urban planning, sustainability, climate action, and smart cities, and key performance indicators such as the NZC Annual Conference, Smart City Expo World Congress & Smart Cities Marketplace Forum, EURESFO, etc. Additionally, events should offer significant networking opportunities with key stakeholders like city planners, policymakers, researchers, and industry leaders, enabling meaningful knowledge exchange and collaboration. The visibility and impact potential of the events are crucial, particularly those that provide platforms for pitching sessions involving all Cluster Projects or applying for joint marketplace spaces. Preference will also be given to events with an established collaborative history, such as EURESFO, where the groundwork for shared participation has already been laid. Geographical and logistical feasibility, as well as strategic timing that fits the Core Cluster's partners, will also be key factors in the selection process. By adhering to these criteria, the projects aim to maximize the effectiveness and reach of their collaborative efforts.

Additionally, a **Community of Practice** structure will be applied to this collaboration, in the realm of knowledge exchange – with the goal of meeting every three months either as a stand-alone meeting or as part of the following activities mentioned below. To get these projects' cities involved, **presentations, and exchange sessions among pilot (and follower) cities** can be organized. For example, **Re-Value has a monthly “Re-Value Rounds” series, and CLIMABOROUGH a series of “CLIMAWebinars”** on which UP2030 could coordinate a presence to exchange urban planning themes. These “Re-Value Rounds” generally gather approximately 30-40 participants, and feed into Re-Value's Community of Practice Approach hosted within its Capacity Development and Exchange Programme.

UP2030 channels (e.g., newsletter, social media) along with those of CLIMABOROUGH and REVALUE will also be used to **cross-promote** events, calls for action, and other outputs for and by the other Cluster Projects.

When it comes to finding cross-cutting themes, the driving goal is to determine the main themes their activities are centred around and to explore potential shared research outcomes and policy recommendations. Regular meetings mentioned above will be used to identify synergies between all levels of the stakeholder landscape, project coordinators and corresponding work package (WP) leaders of each of the Cluster Projects, and the coordination of NZC.

Collaborating across clusters, particularly between the Core Cluster and the Exchange Cluster, is also essential. The Core Cluster can interact with the Exchange Cluster through sharing of project results, participation in common events from the Mission Projects, awareness-raising webinars, and other means of communicating resources produced by the core group. Moreover, the NZC platform is another channel for sharing and communicating their project outcomes.

The Core Cluster will work in close collaboration with members of the Exchange Cluster (as detailed in the section below), including NZC, in order to define synergies and align project results to support the cities developing their transition pathways towards climate neutrality (e.g., Climate City Contracts). This close collaboration will also enable the cities included in the cluster projects to engage and share their

experiences and lessons learned with the Cities Mission. This involves sharing and disseminating project outcomes, **deliverables, and resources on the NZC Portal**, reaching not only Mission Cities but other users of the Portal. As part of D6.12 *Sharing UP2030 best practices and policy briefs with the Mission’s platform*, partners will share project outputs to be displayed on the NZC Portal, functioning as the Cities Mission Platform. The **NetZeroCities annual event** will also be explored as an opportunity for joint presence.

The **Mission Secretariat will be consulted and informed about the progress** of the synergies, as well as any lessons learned, and the key outcomes from this collaboration with the cluster projects and the NZC.

Synergies will also be explored with other relevant initiatives related to the cluster projects and the Cities Mission. Some initiatives include the CoM, Smart Cities Marketplace, and Scalable Cities. The communication working group will look for specific events or calls relevant to these initiatives in order to find opportunities to exchange (e.g. [Smart Cities Expo World Congress](#), Smart Cities Marketplace newsletter, European Week of Regions and Cities). This is strengthened by UP2030 partners’ direct involvement in the organisation of some of such events (e.g. Resilient Cities, ICLEI with European Week of Regions and Cities). These initiatives can support the cities that are part of the cluster projects to up-scale and up-take their projects through their tailored services.

Beyond the Cities Mission, UP2030 and the other projects in the cluster will **seek collaboration with the other Missions, especially the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change** and its related initiatives (i.e., MIP4Adapt). This will allow the cities and communities that are part of both Missions (e.g., Rotterdam, Thessaloniki, etc.) to develop a holistic approach around climate neutrality and urban resilience and other cities to learn from their peers.

Table 4: Core Cluster activities

Core Cluster: Action Points in Summary	
<p>Within Core Cluster</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regular operational Cluster meetings (e.g., every 3 months) • Identification of project outcomes, deliverables of note for further sharing (e.g. with Exchange Cluster) • Simultaneous presence at two or more events • Invitation to UP2030 final conference of Core Cluster projects • Cross-promotion of events and relevant news through Core Cluster project channels • Establishment of Community of Practice: Convene presentations, and exchange sessions among involved cities (e.g., every 3 months) 	<p>Interaction with Exchange Cluster</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing and dissemination of project outcomes, deliverables, and resources on the NZC Portal • Explore synergies with other relevant initiatives to the cluster projects and the Cities Mission. • Seek collaboration with the other Missions, especially the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explore possible common research outcomes or outputs (e.g., policy recommendations) 	
---	--

3.2 Clustering activities with Exchange Cluster

3.2.1 Interactions undertaken

- Net Zero Cities Annual Conference 2023, Brussels, Belgium
- Smart City Expo World Congress & Smart Cities Marketplace Forum 2023, Barcelona, Spain
- Net Zero Cities Annual Conference 2024, Valencia, Spain

The Exchange Cluster has already organised some interactions. At the above-listed events, they shared a common presence at the marketplace, showcasing project results and highlighting upcoming activities and initiatives, thereby fostering collaboration and increasing visibility for their joint efforts in urban sustainability and innovation.

3.2.2 Planned activities

Joint dissemination efforts will begin with the **identification of opportunities, as well as core channels and events** through which UP2030 and other Core Cluster projects can jointly disseminate project activities and results. This will be done alongside the Cities Mission, NZC, and the related Mission projects (e.g., CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value). UP2030 will begin with a **surveying exercise of key project activities on which to focus for joint dissemination**. Upon reaching these milestones, the project aims for the sharing of relevant news, deliverables, or activities with key stakeholders in related Mission projects in the form of **“dissemination packages”** that include relevant messaging, graphics/images, and links.

Table 5: Exchange Cluster Activities

Exchange Cluster Activities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify opportunities and channels/events for joint dissemination alongside Cities Mission, NZC and related Mission projects • Survey key project milestones suited to joint dissemination and create dissemination packages to be shared with Exchange Cluster members

3.3 Documentation of activities

All activities carried out for the implementation of this roadmap must be recorded. Data and information management, as described in the UP2030 Data Management Plan, must be considered. It is proposed to have a **rolling document for the registration of the meetings between the members of the Core Cluster group**, where minutes with identification of tasks and next steps are described. This document will be saved in the SharePoint of the project.

For collaborative activities aimed at identifying cluster topics, interactive digital tools for remote and participatory work can be used. Images or survey results will be collected and stored, and there shall be a record of them, either in a database or an Excel file, where they can be traced.

4 Conclusions

This document provides an initial conceptualisation and plan for clustering activities conducted as part of UP2030. It outlines two different levels of clustering: A “Core Cluster” with CLIMABOROUGH and Re-Value; and an “Exchange Cluster” with a broader range of involvement that includes the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change and associated projects, Relevant Initiatives, and the Cities Mission Secretariat. The contents of this report will be updated in the form of D6.11 Report on clustering activities with other Mission initiatives 2 in M36. The key objectives of these activities are to: **1. Enhance dissemination impact and define cross-cutting themes;** and **2. Raise awareness/impact of the projects to the Cities Mission.**

Next steps include the further elaboration of this document, as well as the initiation of further Core Cluster meetings. During those meetings, activities such as the following are to be explored as opportunities: joint events presence; exchange sessions across projects; exchange of content for cross-promotion; joint presence on the NZC Portal (e.g. through a Groups function); common research outcomes. Further, interaction with the Exchange Cluster will be planned during these meetings: Sharing and dissemination of project outcomes, deliverables, and resources on the NZC Portal; mapping of potential activities to be undertaken with other relevant initiatives and Missions.

In all, clustering activities are intended as an approach to boosting the collective impact of involved projects and initiatives, enhancing the sharing of knowledge and project results, and ensuring wider awareness of the aims and activities therein.